

A Feminist Perspective on Jay Asher's *13 Reasons Why*

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on how female objectification, rape culture, and patriarchy are portrayed and represented in Jay Asher's *13 Reasons Why* (2007). This paper addresses the following questions: 1) How do male characters objectify Hannah Baker, the female major character in the novel? 2) How do *13 Reasons Why* reflect rape culture in American society? 3) How do female objectification and rape culture in the novel represent patriarchy? Therefore, the objectives of this paper are in line with the problems, describing how male characters in the story objectify Hannah Baker, identifying how *13 Reasons Why* reflects rape culture in American society, and arguing how female objectification and rape culture in the story represent patriarchy. To do so, theories of female objectification and rape culture are employed. In addition, since this is a descriptive qualitative study, the main instrument is the writers themselves, who read and scrutinize the text in the light of the theories. After exploration, it is found that male characters in the novel objectify Hannah Baker in several cases. There are also evidence of rape culture in American society as represented in the story. To conclude, the writer finds patriarchy as the root of female objectification and rape culture, a vicious circle.

Keywords: female objectification, rape culture, patriarchy

ABSTRAK

Makalah ini berfokus pada bagaimana objektifikasi perempuan, budaya pemerkosaan, dan patriarki digambarkan dan direpresentasikan dalam *13 Reasons Why* (2007) karya Jay Asher. Makalah ini merumuskan pertanyaan sebagai berikut: 1) Bagaimana karakter laki-laki mengobjektifkan Hannah Baker, tokoh utama perempuan dalam novel tersebut? 2) Bagaimana *13 Reasons Why* mencerminkan budaya pemerkosaan dalam masyarakat Amerika? dan 3) Bagaimana objektifikasi perempuan dan budaya pemerkosaan dalam novel merepresentasikan patriarki? Oleh karena itu, tujuan dari makalah ini adalah, sejalan dengan masalah, menggambarkan bagaimana karakter laki-laki dalam cerita mengobjektifkan Hannah Baker, mengidentifikasi bagaimana *13 reasons why* mencerminkan budaya pemerkosaan dalam masyarakat Amerika dan memperdebatkan bagaimana objektifikasi perempuan dan budaya pemerkosaan dalam cerita tersebut. patriarki. Untuk melakukannya, teori objektifikasi perempuan dan budaya pemerkosaan digunakan. Selain itu, karena ini adalah penelitian kualitatif deskriptif, instrumen utamanya adalah penulis sendiri yang membaca dan meneliti teks berdasarkan teori. Setelah ditelusuri, ditemukan bahwa tokoh laki-laki dalam novel tersebut mengobjektifkasikan Hannah Baker dalam beberapa kasus. Ada juga bukti budaya pemerkosaan dalam masyarakat Amerika seperti yang terwakili dalam cerita. Sebagai

kesimpulan, penulis menemukan patriarki sebagai akar dari objektifikasi perempuan dan budaya pemerkosaan yang dapat dilihat sebagai lingkaran setan.

Kata kunci: objektifikasi perempuan, budaya pemerkosaan, dan patriarki

INTRODUCTION

Literary works are mimesis and represent humans' consciousness, and thought their experiences shape that. One literary work that functions like that is Jay Asher's *13 Reasons Why* (2007). It is a young adult novel. The novel *13 Reasons Why* tells the story of a 17-year-old schoolgirl, Hannah Baker, who commits suicide by cutting her wrist. Before she dies, she records her life stories in thirteen different tapes. Each tape reveals why Hannah has killed herself, and each of the tapes contains one story about her and another person she thinks is responsible for her death. After she dies, her classmate named Clay receives a package with the tapes and an instruction: each person who gets the package must listen to the tapes, and after listening to it, they must pass the package on to the next person on the list. If they break the rule, another package of tapes will be released to the public. Thus, this becomes a mystery who releases the tape after Hannah dies.

As a literary work, *13 Reasons Why* portrays the way teenagers live in a society where patriarchy and bullying related to it is prevalent. We cannot but feel sympathy towards the victim, i.e., Hannah, the novel's main character. She committed suicide because she felt deeply objectified by male characters in the story. She thought they sexually harassed her. One literary criticism that is particularly useful to analyze such a situation is feminist literary criticism.

Feminist criticism is not something new altogether. There are already plenty of them being applied to critically analyze the elements of patriarchy in literary works and beyond. Tanjare McKay, in 2013, wrote "Female Self-Objectification: Causes, Consequences, and Prevention." This article describes self-objectification, self-objectification factors, self-objectification consequences, and the treatment. F.X. Natanael Nonon's *Objectification of Women as Seen Through Anastasia Steel in Fifty Shades of Grey by E.L. James* (2015) focuses on the objectification of women in that particular work. Victoria Eaton in 2016 wrote *Rape Culture in American Society*, where she discusses in-depth the evil culture in America.

METHOD

The paper focuses on how the main female character is portrayed in the novel *13 Reasons Why* by analyzing the story's intrinsic elements and content. The result is presented in the verbal description, and all data are non-numerical. Since the main instrument of this study is the researchers themselves, the analysis process is based on our point of view.

Considering that the primary material being used in this study is a literary work, the applied method is descriptive qualitative. The process of data gathering in this study requires a close reading into that primary resource. Thus, this study is conducted through a library study that includes we, the writers of this paper, reading the story then listing the characters, plots, cases of each chapter of the novel, and all settings in the story which contain female objectification and rape culture based on the stories. After that, we re-read the novel to understand the features better and build a possible bridge with the topics at hand. The third step is we study some secondary sources of data to shed light and lend perspective on the findings

of the reading of the primary material. Lastly, we draw a synthesis between our reading of the primary material and the secondary sources of data to answer the problems of the study.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

THE ISSUE OF FEMALE OBJECTIFICATION

CASSETTE 1: SIDE A

This part of the story describes how Justin Foley objectifies Hannah because she is a female. Justin spreads a rumor about sexual activities that Hannah and he had on their first date. Justin says that Hannah tries to tease him by playing with his zipper. Besides, Justin also claims that he and Hannah make out on their first date, which later Hannah rejects. *"You [Justin] didn't shove your tongue down my throat. You didn't grab my bottom. We just held our lips together...and kissed. And that's it"* (29).

People started humiliating Hannah when the rumor surfaced. They believe more in what Justin says simply because they want to hear, and Hannah has no power to fight Justin back. They start to 'slut-shame' her: *"I know what you're all thinking. Hannah Baker is a slut"* (23). When a woman is labeled as a slut, she is an easy woman. People take her as if she is sexually available to all. Thus, she also becomes a target of unwanted sexual approaches from men, allowing further objectification and sexual harassment toward her.

CASSETTE 1: SIDE B

This part describes the objectification of Hannah because she was a woman by Alex Standall and Bryce Walker. Alex Standall votes Hannah as the Best Ass in the Freshman Class. Alex does this to avenge Jessica Davis, Hannah's best friend, his ex-girlfriend. Alex knows that by putting Hannah on top and putting Jessica's name beside Hannah's (in the "Who's Not" column), Jessica will hate Hannah even more, and this will potentially damage their friendship.

People start to see Hannah only on her specific body part, i.e., her bottom. After the incident, boys at Hannah's school also become more aggressive toward her. One day, for instance, Hannah goes into a store where she bumps into a male senior whose name she hides. That boy smacks Hannah's bottom without feeling guilty. He thinks it is fun to do when he does so, and it pleases him. It is important that his act hurts Hannah's feelings because what he touches is her private body part.

CASSETTE 3: SIDE B

Here, Hannah narrates her *"Oh My Dollar Valentine"* experience with Marcus Cooley. Marcus has a hidden agenda why he invites Hannah to this event. He wants to prove to his friends that Hannah is an easy girl and that he can touch her wherever and whenever he wants to. After some time, Marcus moves his hand along Hannah's upper thigh. Hannah does not move, but when she asks him to stop, he says, *"Don't worry"* and keeps sliding his hand up.

Hannah experiences psychological consequences of being the victim of sexual objectification, as explained below:

THE EMOTION OF ANXIETY

One experiences anxiety when they anticipate danger or threats to themselves. Here, Hannah tries to anticipate further harassment that Marcus could perpetrate. She pushes Marcus away until he falls, but people do not do anything and act as they see it. Hannah feels that people do

not care and let harassment happen. Hannah feels that she cannot trust anyone. *"For the longest time, from almost day one at this school, it seemed that I was the only one who cared about me. Will I always be shoved back and pushed around by those I trust?" (144-145).*

From that excerpt, we know that Hannah expresses her disappointment at people who do not care about the surrounding. She also feels that she cannot ask for help and rely on it. At first, she trusts Marcus, and that is why she accepts the invitation to celebrate valentine's day with him. Unfortunately, it turns out that Marcus only uses Hannah as a bet.

DEMOTIVATING

Due to Marcus' harassing her, Hannah feels that there is no one she can trust and rely on because her friends turn against her and disappoint her. As a teenager, Hannah has a dream she wants to achieve. She feels motivated by that dream. Unfortunately, when she becomes the victim of sexual objectification, she feels reduced to merely an object. Hannah starts to wonder whether she can control her own life.

"Will I ever get control of my life? I decided to find out how people at school might react if one of the students never come back" (145). Objectification leaves Hannah with no motivation to control her life because people keep hurting her feeling. She also thinks that her life means nothing. She starts to wonder how people would react if she did not exist anymore.

CASSETTE 6: SIDE B

Here, it is told how Bryce Walker rapes Hannah inside the hot tub during a party at his house. Bryce objectifies Hannah and uses her as an object to please himself.

Using several key features from Martha Nussbaum and Rae Langton (1995), objectification as experienced by Hannah leaves the victim with negativities such as:

INERTNESS

According to Nussbaum (1995, 257), inertness is defined as lack of activity. When inertness happens, someone turns into a passive and limited person. This passivity happens because the person has no power, as in the case of Hannah: *"But I, for the record, did nothing to stop you ... And then, just like that, I let go. My shoulders went limp. My legs fell apart. I knew exactly what I was doing. I let my reputation catch up with me—I let my reputation become me—with you ... I did not say no or push his hand away. All I did was turn my head, clench my teeth, and fight back the tears... But in the end, I never told you to get away...and you didn't." (263-5).*

VIOLABILITY

In the case of female objectification, since the woman is considered an object, the violator thinks that he does not violate any rule. When Bryce grabs Hannah and his hands play on her body, he sees that Hannah wants him to stop. And yet he keeps rubbing, kissing, and inserting his fingers, without any scruples or guilt because he sees Hannah merely as an object to please him. He also says, *"Just relax," and "Everything will be okay."*

DENIAL OF SUBJECTIVITY

Denial of subjectivity is defined as denying someone's feelings. In Hannah's case, her feeling is ignored by Bryce. The fact that Bryce does not stop what he is doing to Hannah even when he sees Hannah shows repulsive reactions hurts Hannah's mental even worse. Hannah clenches

her jaw tries to move away from Bryce, indicating that she dislikes what Bryce does to her. But, Bryce ignores that Hannah does not want to be touched and her feelings.

REDUCTION TO BODY

Since Hannah's name appears on the list as the best ass in the freshman class, others tend to look at Hannah on her specific body parts only. Boys are particularly interested in that. Reduction to the body here is defined as the treatment of a person as nothing more than the body or the body parts. This means that others will focus on their certain body parts wherever and whenever they go.

SILENCING

Silencing is defined as treating a person as incapable of speaking. Bryce is a sophomore, famous, the captain of the basketball team, and has wealthy parents. Meanwhile, Hannah is a freshman. People tend to see Bryce as a good man, meaning he has a good attitude and good behavior. They will not believe Hannah if she says that Bryce has raped her because he would never rape a girl as a good man. Thus, Hannah cannot convince people that she tells the truth.

THE PROBLEM OF RAPE CULTURE

Rape culture is defined as taking rape against women as common (Olfan, 2009; Flintof, 2001). Rape culture also refers to a condition where people normalize sexual harassment toward women. In *13 Reasons Why*, rape culture can be seen from two cases to Jessica Davis and Hannah Baker. The case where Hannah tries to talk to the school counselor about what has happened to her is also another example of it.

CASSETTE 5: SIDE B

Here, it is told how Bryce Walker rapes Jessica Davis. Jessica is passed out and unconscious because she is drunk from alcohol. Bryce, portrayed as a white guy from a rich family and the captain of the basketball team at Liberty High School, is seen as a good man. And yet, people are blind to the fact that even a guy like him can also be a perpetrator of sexual violence.

Justin, Jessica's boyfriend, is there and even lets Bryce come in and rape Jessica. He gives in to Bryce because Bryce is his good friend. Justin, therefore, can be seen as a manifestation of the idea of rape culture because he normalizes the rape that has been done by Bryce simply because Bryce is an 'alpha man.'

Another evidence of the manifestation of rape culture in this story is when Bryce asks Jessica to relax. Bryce knows that Jessica is unconscious at that time, and she cannot oppose him. He asks Jessica to stay relaxed because doing a sexual activity is a usual thing, and it is normal to him even though he knows he does it without Jessica's consent.

CASSETTE 6: SIDE B

This section talks about how Bryce rapes Hannah inside the hot tub. This rape is called acquaintance rape, which means that the victim is attacked by someone he/she knows (Chancellor, 2012). Hannah does not want to be touched, clenching her teeth in disgust, but Bryce does not care about it.

Bryce normalizes sexual harassment that he does toward Hannah and even other women, and he even considers it a legitimate thing to do by him. As such, we can call Bryce doing individual normalization.

Bryce manifests individual normalization because he represents an individual who takes sexual harassment as legal. He takes rape, and sexual harassment as a normal thing to do by saying, "Just relax," and "*Everything will be fine. He rapes Jessica, Hannah, and other girls without feeling guilty, and no one blames him for doing so*".

CASSETTE 7: SIDE A

Rape culture is also portrayed when Hannah tries to consult with Mr. Porter, her English teacher. Also the counselor for students with last names A until G. Hannah goes to his office and wants to talk about problems that she has. Mr. Porter asks Hannah about what she needs to start the conversation better. Suddenly, Hannah says that she wants everything to stop.

- Well, what do you [Hannah] need right now that you're not getting? Let's start there. I need it to stop".
—You need what to stop?"
—I need everything to stop. People. Life.
—Hannah, do you know what you just said?
—You said you wanted life to stop, Hannah. Your life?
(No response).
—Is that what you meant to say, Hannah? Those are very serious words, you know.
—I know. They are. I'm sorry. (272)

From the conversation between Hannah and Mr. Porter, it can be concluded that Hannah here is giving a clue to Mr. Porter about how things are hard, and she seems like she cannot handle them anymore. Then, Mr. Porter asks Hannah again to tell her opinion about school and people more specifically.

- When you think of school, what's the first thing that comes to mind? Learning, I guess. I'm kidding. I do learn here, but that's not what school is for me.
—Then what is it for you?
A place. Just a place filled with people that I'm required to be with.
—Can you be a little more specific?
It's hard because I don't know who's going to...you know...get me next. Or how.
—What do you mean, "get" you?
I never know when something's going to pop out of the woodwork.
Years ago I was voted... in one of those polls. Well, not really a poll, but someone's stupid idea of a list. A best-of and worst-of thing.
—When was the last time?
Recently. At a party. I swear, one of the worst nights of my life.
—Because of a rumor?
So much more than a rumor. But partly, yes. (273-276)

Hannah tries to tell Mr. Porter that school is not her place. A school is where she has to face people and be friends with, and she thinks it is difficult for her to do so. Hannah feels that one by one, people in her school or her friends will not be her friends anymore and will ruin her life. Hannah tries to tell Mr. Porter that rumors about her and other things can destroy her reputation and her life. Hannah states that not all the issues are rumors, and she tells Mr. Porter about the list that Alex made. Hannah thinks that Alex's list is the beginning of how people objectify her.

Not continuing the story of the list, Hannah moves into the incident at Bryce's house, the party when Bryce rapes her.

—*Can I ask what happened at this party?*

It wasn't really during the party. It was after.

—*At this party you mentioned, are we talking about a boy?*

Yes. But again, it wasn't during the party.

—*I understand that. But we need to start somewhere. I'm not going to judge you, Hannah, but did anything happen that night that you regret?*

Yes.

—*Did anything happen with this boy—and you can be totally honest with me, Hannah—did anything happen that might be considered illegal?*

You mean rape? No. I don't think so.

—*Why don't you know?*

Because there were circumstances.

—*Alcohol?*

Maybe, but not with me.

—*Drugs?*

No, just more circumstances. (276-277)

Hannah does not tell Mr. Porter what happens during the party. When she says about rape, there is an indication that she is not sure whether she has to admit it or not. Thus, she says that she does not think so. On cassette 6: Side B, Hannah admits that she does not say no to Bryce. She shows that she does not like what Bryce does by clenching her teeth and crying. Here, we can infer that Hannah also thinks about being blamed, or in the case of rape culture, it is called victim-blaming. One example of victim-blaming is by saying: "*She did not say no to me.*" Since Hannah admits that she does not say no to Bryce, she could not state whether she was raped or not. But still, the fact that Bryce sees Hannah's cries might be the evidence that he knows that Hannah does not want to do a sexual activity with him.

Mr. Porter continues by asking Hannah what she will do to solve the problem. Hannah does not know what she wants to do; instead, she asks Mr. Porter if he has any options that Hannah can choose.

—*Something needs to be done, Hannah. Something needs to change for you.*

I know. But what are my options? I need you to tell me.

—*Well, if you won't press charges, if you're not sure if you even can press charges, then you have two options.*

What? What are they?

—*One, you can confront him. We can call him in here to discuss what happened at this party. I can call you both out of...*

You said there were two options.

—*Or two, and I'm not trying to be blunt here, Hannah, but you can move on.*

You mean, do nothing?

—*It is an option, and that's all we're talking about. Look, something happened, Hannah. I believe you. But if you won't press charges and you won't confront him, you need to consider the possibility of moving beyond this.*

—*Is he in your class, Hannah?*

He's a senior.

—*So he'll be gone next year. (277-278)*

From the conversation above, we can see that Mr. Porter fails to save Hannah's life because he does not understand Hannah's clues about her being raped by Bryce Walker and wants to commit suicide. Mr. Porter fails to realize that Hannah needs help solving the problem

she is facing. She was raped, and she needs justice. Since Hannah does not want to say clearly the name of the rapist and how this has happened to her, Mr. Porter gave Hannah two options. The first option is to talk to the boy or the rapist (Bryce), and the second option is Hannah should move on and get over it. The second option, when Mr. Porter tells her to move on, Hannah feels that Mr. Porter abandons her. Thus, she decides to take her own life since she sees no alternative to solve her problem.

Furthermore, since Hannah does not want to state the apparent incident and the name of the rapist, Mr. Porter does not have any clue and information required as the data for the school. Hannah does not give details on the incident, such as the name of the rapist or attacker, and even she cannot decide whether it is a rape or not. This makes Mr. Porter cannot take further action, such as reporting it to the police, because Hannah herself does not want to tell him and there is nothing Hannah can do to achieve justice if she does not want to identify the perpetrator. From this case, it can be seen that Mr. Porter, who is also the school representative, cannot go beyond the school policy. Mr. Porter represents structural normalization because he always follows the rules and regulations without giving an exception to the case, which allows him to do so and he makes decisions only based on the regulation and the rule. There has to be a standard of rules or regulations to identify a case or abnormalities, which later will be used by the institution to make a decision or verdict. Structural normalization is manifested by Mr. Porter when he does not report Hannah potentially being raped at school or police because he believes that there must be detailed information and evidence to proceed with the case. When he gets no information or evidence from Hannah, he cannot proceed with the case. Thus, the only thing that he thinks Hannah can do is move on and forget the miserable thing if she does not want to tell the truth and does not want to report it.

In short, Mr. Porter in this story represents the school and manifests structural normalization because he cannot go beyond the school policy. Mr. Porter cannot proceed with Hannah's case because Hannah wants to give clear information and enough evidence. When there is not enough information and evidence, Mr. Porter cannot report to school and police. Thus, he offers Hannah the option to move one if she does not want to tell the incident to Mr. Porter.

PATRIARCHY

Because of patriarchy, female objectification and rape culture happen significantly, albeit partly. In patriarchal culture, men see themselves as the alpha. They gaze and have eyes to see women and later objectify them. *13 Reasons Why* portrays well patriarchy that happens in the society where Hannah lives. Men have significantly unchecked and uncriticized more power in a patriarchal culture than women. That unchecked and uncriticized power facilitates them to treat women without considering that they also have feelings and are full personalities, not only certain body parts.

In this novel, several pieces of evidence prove that patriarchy happens. First, we can see that men tend to have more power because people put more esteem on the words that come out from men's mouths than from women's mouths. For example, in the case where Justin spreads a rumor about what Hannah and he are doing. People at school believe that Hannah is an easy girl, and they start to slut, shaming her without giving her room to explain the truth. Another example is from the case when Bryce smacks Hannah's bottom in the shop; the clerk normalizes what he does to Hannah because a clerk is a man, and he takes the act of Bryce as "boys will be boys" which means that it is a common thing to do by a boy. As the main female

character here, Hannah becomes the victim of patriarchal culture because male characters in the story keep harassing her both physically and verbally.

Moreover, the root cause of Hannah's suicide is firstly and mainly the patriarchy where men's gaze over women is the most dominant drive of the society. In this patriarchal society, men see women and start objectifying them, which leads to sexual harassment and rape in the later stage. After the rape happens, society turns against the victim and begins slut shaming her or blaming the woman as the victim. Thus, patriarchy finds more support. The vicious circle of how patriarchy becomes the starting point that leads to female objectification and rape culture, then later becomes the reason for depression and the suicidal case can be seen below:

Figure 1. The circle of how patriarchy becomes the starting point

From the vicious circle above, it can be seen that patriarchy is the reason why there are female objectification and rape culture. In patriarchy, a man has eyes to see a woman. This leads to female objectification, where a woman becomes the object of the man's eyes. When a woman is being objectified, she becomes the victim of sexual harassment and rape. There are some cases of rape that happen; one example is the rape that Bryce conducts towards several girls. When no one stops him, he keeps raping girls. He thinks that when he rapes girls, it is a normal thing to do because his friend knows his behavior but does nothing. When there is no one stopping Bryce's actions, he will rape girls again and again, which later leads to him normalizing rape or, in this study, the normalization of rape. When people normalize rape and sexual harassment toward women, they take rape and sexual harassment as normal things. When those things happen, they will blame the victim, such as by saying that the woman invites the rapist, the woman does not say no or fight back the rapist, and so on. When Hannah, the victim, cannot do anything anymore, she suffers from depression. People do not believe her story and she cannot report the case. When she gets to the lowest point of her life, she commits suicide.

In a patriarchal society, women are seen as property. Men treat women as properties, and they expect women to provide sexual access to men. Sexual harassment towards women and the consequence of rape culture is one example of how women are treated unequally in a patriarchal culture. In a patriarchal society, women have no control to some extent over their bodies because people normalize sexual harassment or rape that happens to them, and men see themselves as they have the power to see, decide and judge. Women have no power to protect their own bodies. Thus, patriarchy becomes the root of female objectification, leading to sexual

harassment and rape. Along with it, when people see sexual harassment and rape as a normal thing to do, they normalize rape and manifest rape culture.

In addition, when a woman tries to report sexual harassment that happens to her, some people may blame her for the harassment that she suffers and think that the woman who brings the harassment to herself rather than thinking that the male attacker is the one who should take the blame. This kind of victim-blaming becomes a part of rape culture and why women would rather keep silent. Moreover, in a patriarchal culture, male domination leads women to think and believe that they are lesser than men. When they try to speak up, report the case, and tell others, they feel like they are fighting a battle they know they will never win. Thus, in a patriarchal culture, women feel lesser than men, have no power, and are voiceless.

Before Hannah commits suicide, she records thirteen stories as to why she takes her own life. When she is still alive, she has no power to report to the police or other people because she feels that everyone turns against her, which is the aftereffect of each case, starting from the rumors that Justin spreads. However, before she decides to take her own life, she wants people, especially those who have hurt her, to know that they are responsible for her death.

Through her audio recording, she tells people and reports the crime that happens in her life, especially she wants to make people know that Bryce is a rapist because he rapes Jessica and her. By recording her stories, she makes people listen to her. This also becomes Hannah's way of standing up against female objectification, sexual harassment, rape culture, and patriarchy. Furthermore, she takes her own life to emphasize that she suffers so much as she becomes the victim, especially she becomes the victim of rape. She wants people to understand that serious cases are female objectification, sexual harassment, rape culture, and patriarchy. People must stop the vicious circle, so there will be no other victim like her. Therefore, even though Hannah, at the end, commits suicide, she still opposes female objectification, sexual harassment, rape culture, and patriarchy by using her way, recording her stories in thirteen cassettes and mailing them.

CONCLUSION

First, the finding showed female objectification, which is portrayed in several ways. Justin Foley's action is where he spreads sexual rumors about Hannah to make his image cooler. Second, Alex Standall, in his "Hot and Not" List, uses Hannah as a tool to take revenge towards Jessica Davis. Third, Hannah's Valentine dates Marcus Cooley, who uses her to bet with his friends. The last, Bryce Walker, smacks Hannah's bottom in a store and rapes her in the hot tub. Another finding is that this novel represents rape culture. Firstly, Justin's action lets Bryce rape Jessica and never makes a report and tells anyone about it. Secondly, Bryce rapes Jessica and Hannah wherein he manifests individual normalization. Lastly, when Mr. Porter fails in helping Hannah as he manifests structural normalization, he cannot go beyond the rule to find justice for Hannah.

The last finding is that patriarchy becomes the root of female objectification and rape culture, which can be seen in the vicious circle. This circle portrays that patriarchy is why there are female objectification and rape culture. Since men can see women in the patriarchal culture, they put women as objects to please them. They objectify and sexually harass women. When nobody stops those crimes, the perpetrators normalize what they do toward women, leading to the normalization of rape or rape culture. Furthermore, in rape culture, people also do slut-shaming and victim-blaming. When women as victim have no power, they cannot report it to the police and suffer from depression.

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